

Failure of matrix in a composite subjected to multi-axial loads

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ABSTRACT

A new method is presented to predict strength of composites under three-dimensional loading conditions based on component material stress. Matrix failure modes are discussed. In order to analyze the failure and strength behavior of a composite subjected to any load micromechanically, the homogenized stresses in the matrix must be converted into true values in terms of the stress concentration factors (SCFs) of the matrix within the composite. In other words, each of the matrix stresses calculated through a micromechanics model must be multiplied by a corresponding SCF before failure detection for the matrix can be made. The purpose of this paper is to determine the strength of the composite corresponding to three-dimensional loading. First, the matrix's stresses corresponding to the loads are calculated by Bridging Model and modified with the respective SCFs. As the matrix is isotropic, Mohr's theory is then applied to determine the orientation angle of fracture surface corresponding to a biaxial loading. Finally, the matrix real stress components on the fracture surface will be investigated to determine the failure situation. Problems raised in the second world-wide failure exercise (WWFE-II) have been reanalyzed in this paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are used widely in situations of aviation and space industry and complex engineering structure, displaying complex failure modes. Therefore, it is important to develop and complete the composite failure criterion under three-dimensional stresses. However, the research of failure progress of composite under combined loading is still not mature due to the limitations of the research scale and the complication of failure mode. Up to now, most of commercial finite element software used for calculation of the strength of laminates is based on macroscopic strength criterion such as Tsai-Wu criterion, lacking in consideration of the specific component material failure behaviour, with extensive experimental data needed.

Compared with fibre, the failure modes of matrix are much more complicated. It was proposed by Hashin that the fracture of material depends on the stress on the fracture surface [1], which is one of the most important failure hypotheses of Mohr's strength theory. The impact of the damage surface position began to draw attention. Cuntze et al. [2] carried out a series of experiments, pointing out the different influences of positive and negative normal stress on shearing strength. After researching the change of fracture angle with different stress combination, Puck et al. [3] develop a fracture model based on the Mohr-Coulomb criterion. In respect of axial compressive strength, Argon [4] suggested that the real failure infector of composites under axial compression is the shear failure of matrix. Budiansky [5] ascribed this shear stress to fibre initial misalignment and rotation due to shear deformation. D'Avila et al [6] combined methods of Puck and kink band failure theory, followed by Pinho et al. [7] who presented similar model accounts for 3D effects. Thus tensile and shear failure of matrix can cover almost all UD composite failure modes except the simplest fibre axial tensile failure situation.

It is generally realized during research in our own group that fracture angle is a critical parameter for both SCF and the strength prediction. In previous work [8], a candidate SCF was defined as a multiplication of two parts, one related to a line averaged and the other to a surface averaged stress. It was later noticed that the failure surfaces of a UD composite subjected to a transverse tension and compression are different. In the former case the failure surface is perpendicular but in the latter that is

in an inclined angle to the loading direction [9]. The integral direction of SCFs was thus changed into the normal direction of fracture surface [10]. This change brought about great improvement in predicted accuracy. Compared with macroscopic composite mechanics theory, Bridging Model can easily calculate the original stress components in the matrix. Once the SCFs are obtained, the real stress components in matrix are assigned as the original counterparts multiply with them. Although fracture angle under uniaxial transverse loading is considered in calculation of SCFs in previous work, Tsai-Wu's criterion was used to determine matrix failure with fracture surface factor ignored.

Fracture angle factor is introduced into failure judgment process in this paper. A failure model similar to Puck is presented to study matrix compression failure based on the Mohr-Coulomb theory. The difference is that our main searching object is matrix component material instead of the whole composite. As matrix is isotropic, there is only one fracture angle parameter needed, which can be obtained from envelope of matrix. For fiber kinking, an initial misalignment angle based on experimental observations is considered, with an improved further fiber rotation calculated method given. Matrix failure modes are discussed respectively in this paper. Tests raised in the second world-wide failure exercise (WWFE-II) [11] are presented for contrast and analysis.

2 MATRIX TENSILE FAILURE

For composites with perfect interface under any transverse loading, transverse SCFs K_{22} is a function of the fracture plane φ (Fig.1) [10]:

$$K_{22}(\varphi) = \left\{ 1 + \frac{A}{2} \sqrt{V_f} \cos 2\varphi + \frac{B}{2(1-\sqrt{V_f})} \left[V_f^2 \cos 4\varphi + 4V_f (\cos \varphi)^2 (1 - 2\cos 2\varphi) + \sqrt{V_f} (2\cos 2\varphi + \cos 4\varphi) \right] (V_f + a_{22}V_m) / a_{22} \right\} \quad (1.1)$$

$$A = \frac{2E_{22}^f E^m (v_{12}^f)^2 + E_{11}^f \{ E^m (v_{23}^f - 1) - E_{22}^f [2(v^m)^2 + v^m - 1] \}}{E_{11}^f [E_{22}^f + E^m (1 - v_{23}^f) + E_{22}^f v^m] - 2E_{22}^f E^m (v_{12}^f)^2} \quad (1.2)$$

$$B = \frac{E^m (1 + v_{23}^f) - E_{22}^f (1 + v^m)}{E_{22}^f [v^m + 4(v^m)^2 - 3] - E^m (1 + v_{23}^f)} \quad (1.3)$$

E_{11}^f , E_{22}^f , and G_{12}^f are longitudinal, transverse, and in-plane shear module of the fiber, respectively. v_{12}^f , v_{23}^f is its longitudinal and transverse Poisson's ratio. E^m , G^m , and v^m are Young's and shear module and Poisson's ratio of the matrix. V is a volume fraction, with a super-/ sub-script f or m referring to fiber or matrix. Compared with matrix compressive failure, matrix tensile failure mode is relatively simple because fracture face is always perpendicular to the maximum tensile stress direction. Thus the respectively K_{22}^t is the value of Eq.(1.1) with φ to be 0. According to experimental data, interfacial strength plays an extremely important role in this failure mode [12]. For composites with an initial perfect and later deboned interface [13], SCF with cracked interfaces \hat{K}_{22}^t is presented in Eq. (2.1) to predict their tensile failure strength.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{K}_{22}^t(\varphi) = & \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \left[e^{-i\psi} \left(\frac{a^2}{b} - b \right) \left(A - \frac{a^2 k}{b^2} e^{-2i\psi} - ((A - 0.5)b e^{i\psi} + B + \frac{C}{b}) e^{-i\psi} \right. \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{D}{b^2} e^{-2i\psi} \right) \chi(b e^{i\psi}) \right] - \left[\bar{N}_1 \left(\frac{a^2}{a'} \right) - \bar{N}_1 \left(\frac{a^2}{b'} \right) \right] - e^{-2i\psi} (N(a') - N(b')) \right\} e^{-i\psi} \\ & + 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[(N(b') - N(a')) e^{-i\psi} \right] \left\{ \frac{(V_f + 0.3V_m) E_{22}^f + 0.7V_m E^m}{2(b-a)(0.3E_{22}^f + 0.7E^m)} \right\}, \quad (2.1) \end{aligned}$$

$$N(z) = Az + \frac{a^2 k}{z} - (z - a e^{i\psi})^{0.5+i\lambda} (z - a e^{-i\psi})^{0.5-i\lambda} \left[(A - 0.5) - \frac{D}{a^2 z} \right] \quad (2.2)$$

$$N_1(z) = Az + \frac{a^2 k}{z} + \frac{1}{\nu} (z - ae^{i\psi})^{0.5+i\lambda} (z - ae^{-i\psi})^{0.5-i\lambda} \left[(A-0.5) - \frac{D}{a^2 z} \right], \quad (2.3)$$

$$\kappa_1 = 3 - 4\nu^m, \quad \kappa_2 = \frac{3 - \nu_{23}^f - 4\nu_{12}^f \nu_{21}^f}{1 + \nu_{23}^f}, \quad \mu_1 = \frac{E^m}{2(1 + \nu^m)}, \quad \mu_2 = \frac{E_{22}^f}{2(1 + \nu_{23}^f)}. \quad (2.4)$$

Supposing that the interface of the composite is initially bonded perfectly and interfacial cracks appear when the component transverse stress in matrix increase to a critical level $\hat{\sigma}_{22}^m$, the transverse matrix stress corresponding to the composite failure is denoted by $\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^m$, matrix failure occurs when:

$$\hat{K}_{22}^t (\tilde{\sigma}_{22}^m - \hat{\sigma}_{22}^m) + K_{22}^t \hat{\sigma}_{22}^m = \sigma_{u,t}^m, \quad (3.1)$$

$\sigma_{u,t}^m$ is the original tensile strength of matrix.

3 MATRIX SHEAR FAILURE

Figure 1: Stresses of the action plane and fracture angle

In theory, matrix is not expected to fail under hydrostatic compression. Transverse compression failure test is a typical example for proving that matrix failure under compression is due to shear stress component. However, experimental observations show that the fracture surface is not on the 45 degree orientation, where the shear stress component reaches the top. This is because compressive stress acting on the potential fracture plane can improve the shear strength of it. In Fig.1, x_1 -axial is the orientation of fiber. $\sigma_{u,t}^m$, $\sigma_{u,c}^m$ and $\tau_{u,s}^m$ are original tensile, compressive and shear strength of matrix respectively. Supposing that the normal stress on the fracture plane is σ_n^m , the transverse shear stress $\tau_{t,s}^m$ is and the longitude shear stress is $\tau_{l,s}^m$, matrix failure occurs when [14]:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{(\tau_{t,s}^m)^2 + (\tau_{l,s}^m)^2}{(\tau_{u,s}^m)^2} + \frac{(\sigma_n^m)^2}{(\sigma_{u,t}^m)^2} = 1 & \sigma_n^m \geq 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{(\tau_{t,s}^m)^2 + (\tau_{l,s}^m)^2} + \eta \sigma_n^m}{\tau_{u,s}^m} = 1 & \sigma_n^m < 0, \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

η donates the ‘‘internal friction angle parameter’’, which presented the ratio of the improvement of shear strength of fracture surface and the increasing normal compressive stress on it.

3.1 Out-plane shear failure

For combined out-plane loading, the matrix stress components σ_{22}^m , σ_{33}^m and τ_{23}^m could be transversed into two principal normal stresses. If the addition of principal stress is positive, ellipse curve part is chosen as the envelope curve with the parabolic curve chosen for negative condition as Fig.2.

Figure 2: Failure locus envelope of stress circles at failures

Parabolic failure envelope is obtained from matrix shear and compressive strength according to Mohr's theory:

$$\sigma = \frac{-2}{\sigma_{u,c}^m - 4(\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2 / \sigma_{u,c}^m} \tau^2 + \frac{(\sigma_{u,c}^m + 4(\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2 / \sigma_{u,c}^m)^2}{8(\sigma_{u,c}^m - 4(\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2 / \sigma_{u,c}^m)}, \quad (5.1)$$

The fracture face orientation φ can be calculated from principal stresses ratio p of matrix based on matrix envelope and geometrical properties of inscribed circle:

$$p = \frac{\frac{\sigma_{22}^m + \sigma_{33}^m}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}^m - \sigma_{33}^m}{2}\right)^2 + (\tau_{23}^m)^2}}{\frac{\sigma_{22}^m + \sigma_{33}^m}{2} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}^m - \sigma_{33}^m}{2}\right)^2 + (\tau_{23}^m)^2}}, \quad (5.2)$$

$$\varphi = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \arcsin \frac{1}{\frac{1+p}{1-p} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{1+p}{1-p}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,s}^m}{\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m}{4} - (\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2 / \sigma_{u,c}^m}\right)^2}}, \quad (5.3)$$

As a special case of matrix out-plane shear failure mode, for transverse compression, one have $p=0$, thus the φ for transverse compressive SCF K_{22}^c is can be calculated from Eq.(5.3):

$$\varphi = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \arcsin \frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - 4(\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2 / \sigma_{u,c}^m}{\sigma_{u,c}^m + 4(\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2 / \sigma_{u,c}^m} \quad (5.4)$$

The friction angle parameter η can also be obtained from the coordinate of tangent point of parabolic failure envelope with compressive and shear envelope circle:

$$\eta = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - 4(\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2 / \sigma_{u,c}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m}\right)^2} - \frac{2\sigma_{u,s}^m}{\sigma_{u,c}^m} / \left[0.5 + \frac{2(\sigma_{u,s}^m)^2}{(\sigma_{u,c}^m)^2}\right]}. \quad (5.5)$$

3.2 in-plane shear failure

When an UD composite is subjected to a longitudinal (in-plane) shear load, failure surfaces of the matrix are shown in **Fig. 3**^[15, 16]. Hence, the stress averaging line (outward normal to a failure surface) should be in an inclined angle of 45° to the shear stress. From a schematic **figure 3**, we get

$$K_{12}^\varphi = \left[1 - \frac{(G_{12}^f - G^m) \{ \sqrt{V_f} \cos \phi - V_f \sqrt{1 - V_f (\sin \phi)^2} \}}{(G_{12}^f + G^m) \{ \sqrt{(1 - V_f (\sin \phi)^2)} - \sqrt{V_f} \cos \phi \}} \right] \frac{[(V_f + 0.3V_m)G_{12}^f + 0.7V_m G^m]}{(0.3G_{12}^f + 0.7G^m)}. \quad (6.1)$$

Under a transverse load on a CCA model, a is fiber radius, $b = a / \sqrt{V_f}$, the matrix transverse stress component is uniform along the thickness (wherein the x_1 -axial) direction. On the other hand, the

longitudinal shear load applied on the CCA model results in non uniform shear stresses in the thickness (here in the x_3 -axial) direction, as seen in **Fig. 4**. Thus, an average on Eq. (20) along the thickness direction is necessary. This gives to

$$K_{12} = \frac{1}{2a} \int_{-a}^a K_{12}(\varphi)(dx_3) = \frac{1}{\pi a} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} K_{12}(\varphi) \cos(\varphi)(a d\varphi)$$

$$= \left[1 - V_f \frac{G_{12}^f - G^m}{G_{12}^f + G^m} \left\{ W(V_f) - \frac{1}{3} \right\} \right] \frac{[(V_f + 0.3V_m)G_{12}^f + 0.7V_m G^m]}{(0.3G_{12}^f + 0.7G^m)}, \quad (6.2)$$

$$W(V_f) = \int_0^a \frac{1}{a} \sqrt{1 - \frac{x_3^2}{a^2}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{V_f} - \frac{x_3^2}{a^2}} dx_3 \approx \pi \sqrt{V_f} \left[\frac{1}{4V_f} - \frac{4}{128} - \frac{2}{512} V_f - \frac{5}{4096} V_f^2 \right]. \quad (6.3)$$

Fig. 3. Failures of the matrix in a composite under a longitudinal shear^[15,16]

Fig. 4 Schematic for a SCF of matrix under a longitudinal shear

In terms of bridge theory, the composite in-plane shear strength σ_{12}^u is:

$$\sigma_{12}^u = \frac{(V_f + 0.3V_m)G_{12}^f + 0.7V_m G^m}{0.3G_{12}^f + 0.7G^m} \times \frac{\sigma_{u,s}^m}{K_{12}} \quad (6.4)$$

Initial misalignment is a key trigger factor for matrix in-plane shear failure in composites under axial compression. Yurgartis first presented a new measurement method to give an accurate distribution of fibre misalignment [17]. It is found that for the material they measured, 83% of fibre misalignments are less than 1 degree. For the same material, Budiansky[6] assumed that the fibre rotation should be the same as the whole shear strain at failure and deduced fibre initial misalignment of about 2 to 3 degrees. A series of initial misalignments of 3 to 5 degrees were obtained from

measured axial compressive strength with this backstepping-based method. However, according to the distribution measured [17-19], it is extremely hard to find 3 or more neighboring fibre with misalignments larger than 2 degrees. These contradictory evidences indicate that the previous method needs amendment.

The initial misalignment is assumed to be 1 degree here according to experimental observation. Matrix in the in-plane shear model (Fig. 4) is deprecated into two parts based on if their extension part along x_2 axis goes through fibre. On the vertical cross section perpendicular to x_3 axis, according to the 2-D model [20-22], the matrix shearing deformation γ_{12}^m and the fibre rotation angle θ have relationships as follows:

$$\gamma_{12}^m(x_2, x_3) = \frac{\tau_{12}^0}{G^m} \left[1 - a^2 \frac{(G_{12}^f - G^m)(x_2^2 - x_3^2)}{(G_{12}^f + G^m)(x_2^2 + x_3^2)} \right] \quad (7.1)$$

$$\theta(x_3) = \begin{cases} \gamma_{12}^m(x_2, x_3) \times \sqrt{a^2/V_f} / \sqrt{a^2/V_f - x_3^2}, & x_3 \leq a \\ \gamma_{12}^m(x_2, x_3) \frac{\int_a^{\sqrt{a^2/V_f}} \int_0^{\sqrt{a^2/V_f - x_3^2}} dx_2 dx_3}{\int_a^{\sqrt{a^2/V_f}} \int_0^{\sqrt{a^2/V_f - x_3^2}} dx_2 dx_3 + \int_0^a \int_0^{\sqrt{a^2 - x_3^2}} dx_2 dx_3}, & x_3 > a \end{cases} \quad (7.2)$$

According to the definition of K_{12} , matrix shearing failure occurs when:

$$\frac{\tau_{12}^0}{G_m} \left[1 - V_f \frac{G_{12}^f - G^m}{G_{12}^f + G^m} \left\{ W(V_f) - \frac{1}{3} \right\} \right] = \gamma_m^u, \quad (7.3)$$

γ_m^u is the maximum shear deformation of matrix. Thus the fibre rotation angle θ^f can be obtained from integration and averaging from Eq.(7.2) :

$$\theta^f = \gamma_m^u \frac{\left\{ \left[1 - W_1 - \frac{(G_{12}^f - G^m)(W_1 - V_f)}{(G_{12}^f + G^m)} \right] + \left[1 + V_f \frac{(G_{12}^f - G^m)}{(G_{12}^f + G^m)} \right] \right\}}{\left[1 - V_f \frac{G_{12}^f - G^m}{G_{12}^f + G^m} \left\{ W(V_f) - \frac{1}{3} \right\} \right]}, \quad (7.4)$$

$$W_1 = \sqrt{V_f} \left[\frac{97}{120} + \frac{181}{1680} V_f + \frac{27}{560} V_f^2 \right], \quad W = \pi \sqrt{V_f} \left[\frac{1}{4V_f} - \frac{4}{128} - \frac{2}{512} V_f - \frac{5}{4096} V_f^2 \right] \quad (7.5)$$

When V_f is 0.6 the Eq. (7.4). can be reduced to:

$$\theta^f = \gamma_m^u (0.481 + 0.0131 \frac{G_{12}^f - G^m}{G_{12}^f + G^m}) / (1 - 0.359 \frac{G_{12}^f - G^m}{G_{12}^f + G^m}). \quad (7.6)$$

θ_c denotes the addition of initial fibre misalignment and fibre rotation θ^f , thus the normal and shear stress components on the shearing plane can be calculated through rotating coordinate axis. If the composite in-plane shear strength is τ_{12}^u (it can be obtained from Eq. (6.4) or measurement), the axial compression strength σ_{11}^u is:

$$\sigma_{11}^u = \frac{\tau_{12}^u}{\sin(\theta_c) \cos(\theta_c) - \eta \sin(\theta_c) \sin(\theta_c)}, \quad (7.7)$$

If there is transverse compression loading σ_{22} , the failure occurs when

$$\sigma_{11}^0 \sin(\theta_c) \cos(\theta_c) - \eta[\sigma_{11}^0 \sin(\theta_c) \sin(\theta_c) + \sigma_{22}^0] = \tau_{12}'' \quad (7.8)$$

3.3 combined shear failure

Thin-walled tube under torsion and axial compression, as a commonly used object for studying combined failure mode, is a typical failure situation with combined in-plane and out-plane loading [14]. With the ratio of in-plane shear and transverse compressive loading changed from ∞ to 0, the matrix failure mode translate from in-plane shear to out-plane shear. This excessive process of two failure modes is also observed in compression test under changing off-axis angles[23], presented by the change of fracture surface orientation. To find the potential fracture surface in this case, Puck [3] added two "angle parameters" to determine the fracture surface inclination angle. However, these two parameters are obtained from extensive experimental data. The composite experimental strength dates under six different kinds of loading are needed. On the other hand, the fracture surface is determined through trying all angles to choose the one with the minimum predictive strength. The analyses here aim at isotropic matrix, with the only one necessary "angle parameters" obtained from envelope. For matrix with the shear and compressive components σ_{12}^m and σ_{22}^m , after rotating coordinate axis, failure occurs when:

$$\sqrt{(\sigma_{12}^m \cos \varphi)^2 + (\sigma_{22}^m \sin \varphi \cos \varphi)^2} - \eta \sigma_{22}^m \cos \varphi \cos \varphi = \sigma_{u,s}^m \quad (8.1)$$

Set function $f(\varphi)$ about fracture angle φ , $q = \sigma_{12}^m / \sigma_{22}^m$,

$$f(\varphi) = \sqrt{(\sigma_{12}^m \cos \varphi)^2 + (\sigma_{22}^m \sin \varphi \cos \varphi)^2} - \eta \sigma_{22}^m \cos \varphi \cos \varphi, \quad (8.2)$$

Thus the fracture surface with maximum failure potential meets the condition:

$$\frac{d(f(\varphi))}{d(\varphi)} = \sin(2\varphi) \left[\frac{-q^2 + \cos(2\varphi)}{2\sqrt{q^2 \frac{1 + \cos(2\varphi)}{2} + 0.25 \sin^2(2\varphi)}} + \eta \right] = 0, \quad (8.3)$$

thus fracture surface angle can be obtained:

$$\cos 2\varphi = \begin{cases} (q)^2 - \sqrt{(q)^4 - \frac{(\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m)^2 (2(q)^2 + 1)}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m}} \\ 1 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{u,c}^m - \sigma_{u,t}^m}{2\sigma_{u,c}^m}\right)^2}, & q > \eta + \sqrt{1 + \eta^2} \\ 0, & q \leq \eta + \sqrt{1 + \eta^2} \end{cases} \quad (8.4)$$

Once fracture surface is determined, failure stresses can be directly obtained from Eq. (4.1).

4 CONTRAST AND DISCUSSION

Hinton et al.[11]organized the three world-wide failure exercises to assess abilities of the current strength theories for composites with 9 independent material (fibre and matrix) systems considered. All of the fibre and matrix elastic and strength parameters used as input data in this work are shown in Table 1.

4.1 Original component material properties and uniaxial strength prediction

The uniaxial strengths of the 9 UD composites are calculated. Predictions and relative error are summarized in Table 2.

	E-Glass LY556		E-Glass MY750		AS4 3501-6		T300 BSL914C		IM7 8551-7		T300 PR319		AS carbon Epoxy		S2-Glass Epoxy		G40-800 5260	
	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix	Fiber	Matrix
E_{11} (GPa)	80	3.35	74	3.35	225	4.2	230	4.0	276	4.08	230	0.95	231	3.2	87	3.2	290	3.45
E_{22} (GPa)	80	3.35	74	3.35	15	4.2	15	4.0	19	4.08	15	0.95	15	3.2	87	3.2	19	3.45
ν_{12}	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.34	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.38	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.35
G_{12} (GPa)	33.3	1.24	30.8	1.24	15	1.57	15	1.481	27	1.478	15	0.35	15	1.19	36.3	1.19	27	1.28
ν_{23}	0.2	0.35	0.2	0.35	0.07	0.34	0.07	0.35	0.36	0.38	0.07	0.35	0.07	0.35	0.2	0.35	0.357	0.35
$\sigma_{u,t}$ (MPa)	2150	80	2150	80	3350	69	2500	75	5180	99	2500	70	3500	85	2850	73	5860	70
$\sigma_{u,c}$ (MPa)	1450	120	1450	120	2500	250	2000	150	3200	130	2000	130	3000	120	2450	120	3200	130
$\sigma_{u,s}$ (MPa)	-	54	-	54	-	50	-	70	-	57	-	41	-	50	-	52	-	57
V_f	0.62		0.6		0.6		0.6		0.6		0.6		0.6		0.6		0.6	
$\sigma_{11}^{u,t}$ (MPa)	1140		1280		1950		1500		2560		1378		1990		1700		2750	
$\sigma_{11}^{u,c}$ (MPa)	570		800		1480		900		1590		950		1500		1150		1700	
$\sigma_{22}^{u,t}$ (MPa)	35		40		48		27		73		40		38		63		75	
$\sigma_{22}^{u,c}$ (MPa)	114		145		200		200		185		125		150		180		210	
σ_{12}^u (MPa)	72		73		79		80		90		97		70		72		90	

Table 1: Original properties of the 9 UD composites used in WWFEs.

	E- Glass LY556	E- Glass MY750	AS4 3501- 6	T300 BSL914C	IM7 8551-7	T300 PR319	AS carbon Epoxy	S2- Glass Epoxy	G40- 800 5260	Averaged error (%)
$\sigma_{11}^{u,t}$ (MPa)	1367	1329	2035	1517	3139	1504	2119	1752	3544	11.1
$\sigma_{11}^{u,c}$ (MPa)	992	896	1519	929	1665	991	1504	1271	1679	12.6
$\sigma_{22}^{u,t}$ (MPa)	54.2	54.3	52.9	57.1	73.7	48	63.1	49.3	51.3	39.3
$\sigma_{22}^{u,c}$ (MPa)	120.7	121.6	273.9	156	127.9	136.9	119.5	123.9	135.4	23.2
σ_{12}^u (MPa)	81	80.7	70.5	99.2	84	62.3	72	78.3	84.6	13.1

Table 2: Predicted strengths and relative errors in correlation with measured data of the 9 UD composites

Of the 45 predicted strengths, corresponding to which the experimental data are available, present high accuracy. The error of transverse tensile strength is relatively large due to the lack of interfacial tensile strength data.

4.2 Biaxial strength prediction

Some tests in WWFE-II are presented here as examples for strength prediction of composites under three-dimensional loading.

4.2.1 Test case 2

In test case 2, the τ_{12} vs. σ_{22} failure envelope with $\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{22} = \sigma_{33}$ for T300/PR319 is requested. This open envelope indicates that composite is not expected to fail under hydrostatic compression while shear is the real factor for compressive failure. The predicted curve is closed because of a required maximum deformation. It is clear that failure mode with consideration of in-plane shear and normal compression on fracture plane can give accurate prediction for this failure situation.

Figure 5: Failure envelopes for unidirectional composite T300/PR319.

4.2.2 Test case 6 and 7

In test case 6 and 7, the σ_{11} vs. σ_{22} failure envelope with $\sigma_{22} = \sigma_{33}$ for S-glass/epoxy and Carbon/epoxy is requested. It can be seen that axial compression strength increases with hydrostatic pressure. The prediction with fibre compressive failure is far away from the experimental strength indicates that it is not the failure reason. The prediction with Eq.(7.7) is quite accurate for S-glass/epoxy material here. However, it seems that the Carbon/epoxy material axial failure mode of axial compression changes with the increase of hydrostatic pressure. It could also just be a result of the large fluctuation of axial compression test results.

Figure 6: Failure envelopes for unidirectional composite S-glass/epoxy and Carbon/epoxy.

4.2.3 Test case 10 and 11

Test case 10 and 11 requests the τ_{23} vs. σ_{33} envelope for a $(0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_s$ and $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminate of IM7/8551-7. There is a greater fluctuation in the experiment data compared with other tests. It can be observed that the out-plane shear strength increases with the compression from thickness direction at first while drops later because transverse compression gradually becomes the main failure factor.

Figure 7: Failure envelopes for $(0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ)_s$ laminate of IM7/8551-7.

Figure 8: Failure envelopes for $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminate of IM7/8551-7.

5 CONCLUSION

While fibre destroyed by axial tension or compression, there are three different kinds of matrix failure modes: transverse tension, out-plane shear and in-plane shear. For material under transverse tensile and shear, failure stress component does not reach the transverse tensile strength or shear

strength, presenting their cooperation effects; for material under compression and shear, it is important to find the fracture plane, considering the component of out-plane shear and in-plane shear and the protection effect from normal compression on it. With the application of Bridging Model and stress concentration factors, only component material properties are needed for multi-axial loading strength prediction. Following the failure mode in this paper, composites strength corresponding to three-dimensional loading can be predicted with high accuracy. The results indicate that the present theory is believed to be useful in design and development of a composite structure by replacing expensive experiments especially at an initial stage of material selections.

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